

Social inequality in housing allocation during the Soviet era: The case of Soviet Dnipropetrovsk as a high-priority 'closed' metropolis

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Abstract

The article focuses on the forms and patterns of social inequality in the process of administrative housing allocation and access to better housing conditions in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk (modern-day Dnipro, Ukraine). Ideologically, the primary objective of the socialist housing distribution system was to equalise social and regional disparities in living conditions. In practice, however, communist regimes often produced significant housing inequality, typically linked to the status of the city and the social status of the housing recipient. A mixed-method approach is employed, including the analysis of archival documents related to housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, transcripts of in-depth interviews with local residents of Dnipro, and a curated body of relevant scholarly literature. It has been confirmed that in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, due to its high-priority status as a 'closed' city, there was a more pronounced social divide in the process of housing allocation and access, as well as in the quality of living conditions. This concerned not only unequal access to housing among different social groups, but also vertical housing inequality in terms of housing quality. The post-war elitist housing allocation policy laid the foundation for striking social inequality, which was gradually softened during the periods of de-Stalinisation and late socialism.

Keywords

Housing allocation, social inequality, high-priority closed Soviet city, living conditions

Introduction

The study of social inequality in housing allocation and residential disparities under communism, on one hand, and the examination, particularly in recent decades, of the impact of socialist housing distribution on contemporary patterns of housing inequality in post-communist cities, on the other, has become a recurring discursive theme in the scholarly literature. This is especially true for studies focused on the former Soviet Union and other

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countries of the former communist bloc, for which, after post-war Sovietisation, the USSR served as a model for social, economic, urban, and housing policies (Szelenyi, 1978; Morton, 1980; Nechemias, 1981; Bodnár & Böröcz, 1998; Zhou & Suhomlinova, 2001; Tosics, 2012; Gentile & Sjöberg, 2013; Gentile & Marcińczak, 2014; Kalyukin & Kohl, 2020).

“All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others” – a famous statement from George Orwell’s ‘Animal Farm’ (Orwell, 1945) satirises how governments or groups might claim equality while secretly establishing hierarchies or giving preferential treatment to a select few. Ideologically, the primary objective of the Soviet housing distribution system (as in other communist countries; hereinafter the term ‘communist’ indicates ‘ruled by a communist party’) was to provide each family of the ‘builders of communism’ with separate housing and to equalise social and regional disparities in living conditions. In practice, however, the reality was quite different. Researchers have confirmed the existence of housing inequality under communist regimes, often linked to the status of the city and the social status of the housing recipient. Nevertheless, the extent of this inequality varied significantly from country to country, and even from city to city within the same country (Szelenyi, 1983; Morton, 1984a; Morton, 1987; Alexeev, 1988; Becker et al., 2012).

Socialist practice distorted socialist ideas, including the ideal of socio-economic equality. Rather than providing everyone with equal opportunities in the geographical space of the country, cities were transformed into ideological instruments of the centralised planned economy (Frost, 2018). Consequently, the former socialist countries and their cities faced the timeless question encountered by all differentiated societies of how to distribute scarce urban resources and amenities, in particular, who would live in the more environmentally and geographically favourable parts of the cities, who would have access to the better segments of the housing stock, and who would benefit from superior technical and social urban infrastructure (Musil, nd). Socialist cities were generally free from explicit manifestations of social (ethnic, racial, or class) segregation; nevertheless, as Soja (2010) points out, redistributive injustice can operate without rigid forms of spatial segregation.

In studies on housing inequality under state socialism, three main thematic dimensions can be distinguished. The first two aspects encompass research on housing inequality in socialist cities (Hegedüs & Tosics, 1983; Morton, 1987; Dangschat & Blasius, 1987; Musil, 1987; Colton, 1995; Kulu & Tammaru, 2003; Ruoppila, 2004; Gentile & Sjöberg, 2013; Archer, 2016) and post-socialist cities, where, as numerous empirical studies show, housing inequality was largely shaped by patterns of social inequality embedded in housing distribution practices during communist rule (Gentile, 2015; Leetmaa et al., 2015). The third thematic dimension involves the study of housing inequality across cities of different ranks within the urban

hierarchy of centrally planned economies. Examples include Poland (Zaniewski, 1991), the USSR and its constituent republics (Nechemias, 1981; Andrusz, 1984; Morton, 1984b), as well as broader comparative studies within the communist bloc (Zaniewski, 1989). It also includes research on the uneven distribution of housing within individual countries and international comparisons (Morton, 1984a; Szelenyi, 1987; Zhou & Suhomlinova, 2001; Matthews, 2011).

Nevertheless, the scholarly discourse on housing distribution in communist cities lacks sufficient attention to the case of Soviet Ukraine, particularly to the distinct mechanisms of housing allocation in highly privileged ‘closed’ cities. Accordingly, the main objective of this study is to investigate the Soviet experience of social inequality in housing distribution processes – which generated housing inequality within a supposedly egalitarian Soviet society – focusing on the case of a highly privileged, ‘closed’ million-plus city of the former USSR: Dnipropetrovsk (now Dnipro), Ukraine.

The eternal question of Shakespearean Hamlet, on which the mere life depended, was ‘To be or not to be?’ Similarly, Morton (1980) posed seminal question regarding housing allocation in the Soviet Union: “Who gets what, when and how?”, drawing attention to the mechanisms of distribution and access within the planned system. This inquiry can be narrowed down to: “Who received better housing in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, when, and why?” More specifically, the following research questions can be formulated:

- (1) Did social inequality exist in the process of administrative housing allocation and access to better housing conditions in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, and how did this inequality change over time?
- (2) What personal attributes did an individual need to possess in order to receive housing in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk?
- (3) What socio-spatial characteristics of housing allocation were present in the city of Dnipropetrovsk as a high-priority ‘closed’ metropolis, and how did they distinguish it from other open cities of the Ukrainian SSR/USSR as a whole?

The main research hypothesis is as follows: The process of administrative housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk was marked by significant social inequality, and the city’s status of a high-priority ‘closed’ metropolis contributed to the intensification of housing-related social inequalities during the Soviet era.

Theoretical background

Housing inequality in the context of spatial fairness and spatial justice

Housing inequality is a persistent and pressing issue in many parts of the world (Tan et al., 2016; Nasrabadi et al., 2024), and it is considered a major source of material inequality in many

societies (Atkinson & Jacobs, 2022). The concept of housing inequality is an expansive one that has been used within an array of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary contexts, from sociology, economics, and urban planning to public health (Nasrabadi et al., 2024). In the most general sense, housing inequality refers to unequal access to adequate, affordable, and secure housing and homeownership across different socioeconomic groups. This includes physical quality of housing (Aitken et al., 2019), housing tenure (Wiesel et al., 2021), availability of affordable and decent housing (James et al., 2022), the possibility of choosing the location and type of housing (Grander, 2021), and various neighbourhood amenities (Bower et al., 2021; Grander, 2021; Havryliuk, 2022). The factors contributing to housing inequality typically include economic situations, socio-demographic characteristics, and racial or ethnic segregation (Mirkatouli et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2023; Emblad 2025). Since housing inequality may lead to increased segregation, reduced economic mobility, and a perpetuation of poverty cycles, understanding the causes and impacts of housing inequality is essential for developing strategies to promote fair housing practices and ensure equitable living conditions for all. More specifically, the term housing inequality can be interpreted in at least two ways: first, as a difference in housing consumption, that is who receives better and more valuable housing, and second, as a difference in housing subsidies, that is who receives more or less public support (Hegedüs, 1988). In the present study, the authors use the term housing inequality in the first sense.

The issue of housing inequality is tightly interconnected with the idea of the fairness of housing allocation, which in turn constitutes an aspect of spatial fairness. The latter can be understood as a set of norms, principles, and practices that determine who receives housing, when, and what type of housing, and whether this process is considered justified and legitimate in societal perception. For example, possible forms are need-based fairness (housing is allocated primarily to those who need it most), merit-based fairness (housing is provided to those who have earned it more – through work, seniority, achievements, or contribution to society), and market-based fairness (if one has the resources to purchase housing, the right to housing is considered fair) (Váně, 2020; Wolter, 2024). In socialist cities (particularly in the USSR), need-based fairness was formally declared, as in the well-known slogan ‘from each according to ability, to each according to need’, although in practice, social status and influence played an important role.

In turn, spatial fairness can be regarded as one of the dimensions of another concept, spatial justice. In this case, the focus is not only on the procedural integrity in distributing a given public good, but also on the deeper structural question of how space itself and spatial decisions reproduce or challenge social inequalities. Spatial justice emphasises the equitable

distribution of resources, opportunities, and services, as well as the right of individuals and communities to inhabit and use space in a beneficial, fair, and sustainable way (Capra-Ribeiro, 2024; Feitosa et al., 2024; Dadashpoor & Dehghan, 2025).

Housing inequality in socialist countries

During World War II, a significant share of the housing stock in Central and Eastern Europe was destroyed, resulting in a housing collapse in many communist cities during the post-war reconstruction period. The already devastated urban infrastructure was further burdened by mass waves of military demobilisation and labour migration. As a result, improving the housing situation and expanding social infrastructure in both urban and rural areas became a top priority for communist governments. Between 1950 and 1990, approximately 14 million apartments were built in Central and Eastern Europe, while 66 million apartments were constructed in the former USSR (Šuška & Stasíková, 2013).

Numerous studies confirm the existence of housing inequality in the distribution of housing in communist countries – often depending on the status of the city and the social status of the housing recipient – although the degree of such inequality varied both between cities and across countries (Szelenyi, 1983; Morton, 1984a; Morton, 1987; Alexeev, 1988; Becker et al., 2012). Socialist cities in Central Europe experienced pronounced socio-spatial effects due to the redistributive nature of centrally planned economies, the absence of land markets, and the specific features of socialist housing policies (Musil, 1993):

- City centres underwent significantly fewer physical and functional changes compared to cities of similar size in market-based economies;
- Cities in former socialist countries were fundamentally reshaped by the construction of large-scale housing estates, which were much larger than those in capitalist cities (in the socialist countries, standardised series of panel and brick apartment buildings were mass-produced; the idea of the microrayon (a planned residential neighbourhood unit in modernist urban planning, designed to provide housing together with essential services and amenities within walkable distance) dominated, which required the simultaneous development of large territories; since land had no market value, developers did not economise on space and could allocate vast areas for uniform residential construction);
- Socio-spatial differentiation in socialist cities was driven by factors that were different from, yet also similar to, those observed in capitalist cities (as we argue through the paper, in socialist cities, socio-spatial differentiation was primarily driven by state-led planning and resource allocation, as well as the official

egalitarian state politics, with practically zero role of real estate market mechanisms, leading to a more uniform distribution of social groups and a focus on large-scale housing projects with relatively low internal social segregation, though hidden inequalities existed). Undeniably, a certain level of social segregation existed;

- The role of socio-economic status in shaping socio-spatial differentiation was less pronounced in socialist cities than in capitalist ones and was often less significant than family-related factors (family status, for example, age, marital status, presence of children became the main condition for obtaining an apartment (Kubeš, 2013));
- Due to changes in socialist housing policy in the 1960s and beyond, a growing income disparity, and the emergence of a mixed socialist housing system with strong market elements (often through informal or black-market mechanisms), new patterns of socio-spatial differentiation began to emerge. On one hand, elderly residents and low-income households were increasingly concentrated (even trapped) in decaying city centres, while Roma populations were often located in many older residential areas within central urban zones. On the other hand, newly built housing estates in Czechoslovakia and East Germany (but not in Poland or Hungary) exhibited relatively high degrees of social heterogeneity. Further differentiation also developed on the basis of pre-war villa districts and new private residential developments on the urban peripheries. Some of these new patterns of differentiation were associated with the slowly re-emerging processes of suburbanisation.

Overall, most of these effects can be partially extended to the broader experience of socio-spatial urban transformations across other socialist countries in Europe, including the European territories of the former Soviet Union.

Housing inequality in socialist cities cannot be attributed solely to the policies of governments in various communist countries, as inherited pre-socialist models of housing inequality also had a certain influence on the housing conditions in these cities. Among other factors: the replacement of market-based distribution with administrative allocation may simply substitute one mechanism of inequality for another; administrative allocation may at times replicate the imbalanced market mechanisms it was intended to replace and transform; inequalities in administrative allocation, as well as the resulting disparities, may have become inevitable once wage policy was implemented (Szelenyi, 1983). Furthermore, the development of socialist cities did not always challenge the capitalist past but rather continued its socio-

spatial patterns, particularly within the inner city. In turn, inherited pre-socialist socio-spatial structures in socialist cities were characterised by high-status residential areas in urban centres, certain old town districts, and garden suburbs. Generally, socio-economic status tended to decline from the centre toward the periphery, reaching its lowest levels in working-class districts located near manufacturing zones (Ruoppila, 2004).

Furthermore, in socialist countries, access to housing was stratified by educational and professional qualifications. For example, in Hungary from the mid-1940s to the 1970s, public housing distribution was clearly stratified according to socio-professional status: professionals, white-collar employees, and highly skilled workers received state-built apartments, while working-class individuals, especially semi-skilled and unskilled labourers, were expected to construct their own homes (Szelenyi, 1978). Another example is socialist Warsaw, where better-educated individuals received state or cooperative housing after a shorter waiting period (Dangschat & Blasius, 1987). Soviet Tartu, Estonia, based on 1989 census data, similarly demonstrates that higher-educated individuals enjoyed better housing quality, and that workers in the industrial and construction sectors were more likely to receive state housing and improve their housing conditions than those in the service sector (Kulu & Tammaru, 2003). These and other cases clearly support the view that housing under actually existing socialism was distributed unequally. First, those who were better educated and higher in the professional hierarchy had better chances of securing better housing (Szelenyi, 1987). Second, in the USSR's so-called 'classless society', with modest differences in monetary income, residential location was a primary indicator of status. The size of the apartment, proximity to the metro or city centre, and housing quality spoke not of residents' earnings, but rather of their social connections (Becker et al., 2012).

Generally, in the Soviet Union, there were two main ways of acquiring a flat in a newly constructed apartment building: renting from the state (or an institutional landlord) or purchasing a cooperative apartment. Notably, state housing was constructed by agencies and municipalities and remained under their ownership (Gunko et al., 2018). More broadly, from 1924 onward, housing ownership in the USSR was categorised into four types: local councils (the former 'municipalised' sector); state ministries, enterprises, and trade unions (the previously 'nationalised' sector, later becoming the 'departmental' housing stock); housing cooperatives; and private ownership. The distinction between the first and second categories lay in the fact that local councils distributed housing within their administrative jurisdictions, whereas departmental housing was allocated to those with 'productive relations' with the respective institutions (Andrusz, 1992). On one hand, departmental housing was allocated to employees of specific enterprises or organisations and to certain legally defined privileged

groups (e.g., Heroes of the Soviet Union, ‘Mother-Heroines’ renowned figures in science and the arts). On the other hand, the formal procedures for accessing municipal and departmental housing were almost identical, except that queues for municipal housing tended to be significantly longer (Gunko et al., 2018). Enterprises that financed housing construction would often transfer newly built properties to local authorities, but still insisted on retaining the right to select initial tenants, and sometimes even their successors. They also used the housing stock as a tool to attract qualified workers and managerial staff (McAuley, 1984).

Furthermore, housing inequality in the USSR was also observed between Communist Party members and non-members. Where employers controlled housing, party members were often rewarded for their routine and ‘diligent’ service with priority access to available apartments; municipal committees overseeing most housing stock were also instructed to prioritise party members (Seeger, 1984). For instance, in Soviet Russia, individuals with political influence or alternatives (such as the ability to delay accepting an assigned apartment until a better option became available) typically secured better housing. Those employed at prominent enterprises or government ministries usually had better housing opportunities than those working in lower-priority institutions. Nevertheless, housing allocation also involved a degree of randomness: if one’s place in the housing queue coincided with the completion of a new development, the quality of the assigned apartment would be higher than those available during periods of acute shortages (Becker et al., 2012).

Soviet housing distribution was also marked by informal practices. Residents seeking better housing would attempt to enter the city housing allocation waiting list. Eligibility usually began at five square meters or less per family member. Given that state officials controlled a limited housing supply, housing bureaucrats became frequent recipients of bribes. Jumping the queue was a widespread aspiration, as it could reduce the waiting time from ten years to zero – requiring influence, a bribe, or both (Morton, 1984b). Additionally, both in the USSR and other socialist countries, so-called vertical housing inequality (or rather vertical inequality of housing conditions) was evident, reflecting broader social inequality in access to superior dwellings. For example, top-floor apartments in prefabricated socialist apartment blocks were often stigmatised due to problems with leaking roofs (Gentile & Marcińczak, 2014).

Socio-spatial stratification under socialism: a place of ‘closed’ cities

In the Soviet Union, a three-tier hierarchical socio-spatial stratification existed (figure 1). To paraphrase Smith (1989), the least privileged social stratum comprised the peasantry, who had significantly poorer life prospects and fewer opportunities for upward social mobility compared to the residents of ‘open’ towns and cities. However, neither group could relocate to the highly

privileged 'closed' cities without official residence registration (*propiska*). The 'closed' cities housed the most privileged segment of the Soviet population, as these cities offered markedly higher living standards (especially in Soviet Moscow and Leningrad), better access to goods and services, and significantly greater opportunities for upward mobility. As a result, 'closed' cities

Figure 1: Class-related territorial stratification of localities in the USSR
(A – scheme according to Smith (1989, p. 332); B – authors' revision based on literature review)

became hubs for highly skilled and professional labour. The continuous industrial growth of these 'closed' cities was, however, achieved at the expense of underinvestment in 'open' cities and towns (Gentile 2004; Portnov & Portnova 2015).

In addition, the social dimensions of urban housing in the USSR were marked by inequalities in living conditions along the urban hierarchy. While Soviet urban districts may have appeared uniformly drab to the casual observer, important social distinctions were hidden behind their grey facades. There is no reason to assume that any major Soviet city lacked prestige housing. Housing quality was as significant as its quantity or type. Generally, housing standards - outside of Soviet Moscow and other large cities - were quite low (Matthews, 1979). The level of urban infrastructure development in Soviet cities positively correlated with city size and the percentage of state-owned housing, with Soviet Moscow offering the best housing standards. Conversely, lower levels of infrastructure were typical of towns with populations under 50,000, which had higher rates of private housing compared to medium and large cities (Jacobs, 1976). Such disparities in urban infrastructure between high-priority cities and other urban settlements in the Soviet urban hierarchy were a direct consequence of long-standing Soviet housing policies.

Similar disparities in urban housing standards were observed in other socialist countries. For instance, in socialist Poland, housing conditions in small and agricultural towns were markedly worse than in larger industrial cities. This was an outcome of the heavy industrialisation policies of the 1950s, which prioritised housing construction and modernisation programs in large and medium-sized cities (Zaniewski, 1991). Nearly half of the

working class in Hungary – and figures were similar in other CEE countries, particularly Poland and Czechoslovakia – never had the opportunity to move to cities due to their inability to purchase housing or qualify for state housing, remaining in villages in privately owned, inherited, or self-built dwellings (Szelenyi, 1978).

As Morton (1984b) emphasises, in the eyes of most Soviet citizens, the city represented the most desirable – if not the only desirable – place to live, and the larger the city, the better, with Moscow or capitals of the Soviet Union constituent republics regarded as ideal. At the same time, millions of people residing in satellite communities near large cities often constituted the urban underclass of Soviet society – not due to unemployment, but because of poor access to consumer services: limited variety and quality of goods, chronic food shortages (especially of meat and dairy products), and a lack of restaurants, cinemas, theatres, adequate healthcare facilities, and repair services. Such amenities were either absent or available only in large cities.

It is important to stress that strategic closed enterprises and ‘closed’ cities also contributed significantly to social inequality in access to housing, as well as to better food supplies and infrastructure. As Zaslavsky (1988) argues, Soviet closed enterprises and cities represent an example of state-engineered stratification. In these cases, the party-state apparatus erected barriers between social categories through security clearance for employment at closed enterprises and residential registration (*propiska*) for settlement in ‘closed’ cities. The party-state controlled movement between these categories by setting quotas and regulations and overseeing their enforcement; it ranked these subgroups by allocating privileges to some, while relegating others to lower tiers of the socio-economic hierarchy (including the hierarchical organisation of cities into tiers of food and consumer goods supply, and manipulation of housing investment allocations).

In conclusion, the research gap in this field that still requires scholarly attention concerns the evolutionary and path-dependence perspective on social inequality in housing allocation in socialist (particularly Soviet) cities, especially those with a ‘closed’ status. Path dependence here is understood as the long-term persistence or momentum effect of once-established trends or patterns, shaping the specific trajectories of urban development in Central and Eastern Europe (Ruoppila, 2004). This article represents an attempt to fill this gap by explaining how the status of a high-priority ‘closed’ metropolis contributed to the intensification of housing-related social inequality in the city of Dnipropetrovsk during the Soviet era.

The research case: Dnipropetrovsk as a high-priority Soviet metropolis

Dnipro (known as Dnipropetrovsk from 1926 to 2016) is an industrially developed metropolis in Ukraine that possessed certain unique features of development during the socialist era. After World War II, Soviet Dnipropetrovsk experienced rapid growth, and by the era of late socialism, it became one of the five million-plus cities in the Ukrainian SSR, as well as one of the largest ‘closed’ cities in the Soviet Union – an exceptional case within the broader context of state policies aimed at controlling urban population size (Clayton & Richardson, 1989).

Dnipropetrovsk was granted its special status as a ‘closed’ city due to the presence of strategic military industrial enterprises, such as *Pivdenmash* (Southern Machine-Building Plant) and *Pivdenne Design Bureau*, which were engaged in the design, production, and testing of missile systems during the Cold War (Beyer et al., 1986; Chertok, 2006; Zhuk, 2010; Siddiqi, 2016; Portnov & Portnova, 2017; Kulick, 2019; Gubka & Savchuk, 2020). Since the early 1950s, many ostensibly civilian enterprises in the city began operating classified production lines for military use, such as the Dnipro Machine-Building Plant, which produced military radar systems. The concentration of such restricted-access defence enterprises, and particularly missile construction at *Pivdenmash*, led to Dnipropetrovsk being closed to foreigners – including those from other communist countries – from 1959 to 1989. Even foreign tourists and students were barred from entry (Portnov & Portnova, 2014; Portnov, 2015; Portnov & Portnova, 2017). Most residents of the ‘missile city’ believed that the ‘closed’ city status affirmed the importance of *Pivdenmash* and granted certain privileges, for example, significantly better supplies in local stores compared to other ‘open’ Soviet cities (Portnov & Portnova, 2015).

In addition, Dnipropetrovsk also played a significant role in the political life of the Soviet Union, as it became a ‘breeding ground’ for numerous Soviet politicians who later pursued careers in Moscow and Kyiv. The status and privileges of the city were further reinforced and somewhat mythologized by the fact that in 1964, a ‘man from Dnipropetrovsk’, Leonid Brezhnev, who had served as the First Secretary of the Dnipropetrovsk Regional Committee of the Communist Party of Ukraine from 1947 to 1950, was appointed head of the Soviet state (Frank, 1987; Miller, 1989; Dukes, 1998; Zhuk, 2008; Zhuk, 2012; Portnov & Portnova, 2015; Portnov & Portnova, 2017; Kulick, 2019). Furthermore, the Union-Republican Ministry of Ferrous Metallurgy of the Ukrainian SSR was headquartered in Dnipropetrovsk (1964-1987), further affirming the city’s strategic importance within the economic landscape of both the Ukrainian SSR and the broader Soviet Union.

In line with Zaslavsky (1988), the authors contend that a major Soviet ‘closed’ city such as Dnipropetrovsk represents an underexplored case of multidimensional and complex social

inequality, especially in terms of housing distribution and access to superior living conditions. The Dnipropetrovsk case demonstrates that territorial stratification arising from the vast system of ‘closed’ and ‘open’ cities and villages in the Soviet Union was not simply a matter of unequal distribution of privileges and resources. By the early 1970s, a strong symbiosis had formed between the Military-Industrial Commission, the Politburo, the Secretariat, and officials originating from Dnipropetrovsk. As a result, individuals with ties to the region assumed prominent positions within the Kremlin (Kulick, 2019), contributing to a mythologized link between this high-priority ‘closed’ city and the ruling elite.

Previous studies have revealed that the localisation of high-priority enterprises in Dnipropetrovsk contributed to better infrastructural provision in the city and to significant differences in the quality of housing stock for employees of these enterprises (Zhuk, 2010; Kulick, 2019). Apartment buildings for engineers and specialists working at *Pivdenmash* were constructed with higher-quality materials (brick instead of concrete panels) and were warmer during the winter. Greater attention was given to the planning of residential neighbourhoods, transportation infrastructure, the placement of shared spaces and playgrounds; there was more supervision and quality control during construction, as well as a larger construction budget (Kulick, 2019).

Based on the above, it can be assumed that the status of Dnipropetrovsk as a high-priority ‘closed’ Soviet metropolis contributed to the intensification of social inequality in the area of housing distribution during the Soviet era.

The modern spatial structure of Dnipro consists of three historical layers: pre-Soviet, Soviet, and post-Soviet. At the same time, the internal spatial structure of the city can be considered through the lens of its central, semi-peripheral, and peripheral zones. The historical centre and, more broadly, the central zone is characterised primarily by late 19th–early 20th century buildings, containing fragments of Soviet and post-Soviet development. The relative area of this part of the city is small, but it has high population density, a concentration of administrative, cultural, and commercial facilities, and it is currently undergoing intensive manhattanisation (the rapid construction of many tall, densely situated buildings, which fundamentally alters its appearance and character to resemble Manhattan, New York City, resulting in a dense, vertical cityscape with a significant presence of high-rise structures) and gentrification. Soviet-era residential neighbourhoods (e.g., Topolya, Chervony Kamin, Parus, Soniachnyi) are mainly located in the semi-peripheral zone of the city, adjacent to private houses also built during the Soviet period. These districts occupy up to one-quarter of the city’s total area but constitute the majority of its housing stock. Most of this development consists of classic Soviet microrayons with panel and brick apartment buildings, constructed after World

War II, during the 1950s–1980s. The peripheral part of the city, occupying almost half of its total area, is predominantly covered by low-density detached housing, including dacha settlements and recently built cottages. Post-Soviet multi-storey housing occurs sporadically throughout the city, while recent detached housing developments are concentrated mainly on the periphery (see Havryliuk, 2022).

Data and methods

The study employs a mixed-method approach combining three core research methods to answer the proposed research questions and to test the formulated hypothesis. The primary data sources include archival documents concerning housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, transcripts of in-depth interviews with local residents of Dnipro, and a curated body of literature relevant to the topic. These data are instrumental in identifying historiographical patterns and intra-urban processes of housing allocation during the periods of post-war Stalinism (1945–1953), de-Stalinisation (1953–1964), and late socialism (1964–1985) in Dnipropetrovsk.

In May–June 2019, a field study was conducted in Dnipro, during which archival materials of the Dnipropetrovsk City Executive Committee’s decisions on housing allocation during the Soviet era, stored at the State Archive of the Dnipropetrovsk Region, were examined. Specifically, decisions from selected periods of 1950, 1960, 1970, and 1979 were analysed, representing different phases of post-war Stalinism (1945–1953), de-Stalinisation (1953–1964), and late socialism (1964–1985). A database of housing recipients in Dnipropetrovsk for these years was compiled based on digitised resolutions, in accordance with Ukrainian legislation on personal data protection, yielding a sample of 616 recipients: 185 in 1950, 297 in 1960, and 134 combined in 1970 and 1979. The analytical categories used in the analysis of archival materials included the date of the document, the living area, the number of rooms in the dwelling, the family composition, and the social and professional status of the housing recipient(s), where such information was available. Unfortunately, it was impossible to locate specific housing waiting lists for Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, as Michael Gentile and Örjan Sjöberg (2013) did in their study of Soviet housing allocation in Daugavpils, Latvia. Nevertheless, this in no way diminishes the scholarly significance of the results obtained from the analysis of 616 housing recipients in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk.

Participants for the in-depth interviews in this study were active participants in a sample questionnaire survey of adult (18+) residents of Dnipro (n = 1,258), conducted in early 2018. The survey was initiated by the University of Oslo (Norway) and carried out on a contractual basis by the ‘Centre for Social Indicators’ (CSI), affiliated with the Kyiv International Institute of

Sociology (KIIS). This was a face-to-face survey that, among other topics, included a question on housing. During data coding and analysis, respondents were guaranteed full anonymity; accordingly, the dataset does not contain names or addresses, in compliance with current Ukrainian and Norwegian legislation on personal data protection. In addition, the snowball method was used. In-depth interviews with Dnipro residents were conducted in November 2020 (Table 1). The primary aim of these interviews was to capture the lived experience of obtaining housing in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, since archival sources alone are insufficient to assess the impact of the ‘closed city effect’ on housing inequality among different social groups in socialist society. Each in-depth interview lasted approximately 1–2 hours. The main codes used for the analysis of the interview transcripts included: the time of being placed on the housing waiting list; the time of actual receipt of housing; factors that influenced the speed of obtaining housing or the quality of housing by the participant or their relatives or acquaintances (e.g. age, gender, professional, family, or party status, place of origin, employment at a strategic enterprise, participation in housing construction); positive or negative feedback regarding the quality of the received housing and living conditions, in particular the unequal quality of housing on different floors, in standard and corner apartments, etc.; legal and shadow ways of influencing housing allocation procedure.

Table 1: Characteristics of interview participants from Dnipro

ID	Sex	Age	Education
HD1	F	50	higher
HD2	M	73	higher
HD3	F	79	secondary
HD4	M	66	higher
HD5	F	63	higher
HD6	F	52	higher
HD7	F	30	higher

The authors acknowledge that the interview data primarily reflect intra-urban housing distribution patterns during the late socialist period, which marked the ‘golden age’ of this ‘closed’ Soviet city. At the same time, the specific patterns of housing distribution inequality in other Soviet ‘closed’ cities may have been somewhat different. Another limitation of this study is that the interview materials relate almost exclusively to the late socialist period; therefore, the conclusions drawn from the archival materials remain uncorroborated by in-depth interview evidence.

The concise literature review serves a supplementary and clarifying role for a better understanding of the context of each historical period, including dominant housing construction technologies employed and state policies in the field of housing construction and distribution.

Housing allocation

Housing allocation in Dnipropetrovsk in the post-war Stalinist period (1945-1953)

During the Stalinist era, providing decent housing conditions for the broader population was not among the state's priorities (Iankovska & Bachynskyj, 2013), and the pace of post-war housing reconstruction failed to meet the population's needs (Iankovska, 2008). In the Soviet Union, the 'net living space' indicator was used, which accounted only for the area of living rooms and bedrooms. Between 1923 and 1950, the average net living space per urban resident in the USSR decreased from 6.45 to 4.67 m² (Wright, 1970).

Archival materials indicate that in post-war Dnipropetrovsk, housing was primarily allocated to demobilised individuals (including WWII veterans), families of those killed on the front, military personnel, figures of science and the arts, and members of the nomenklatura (e.g., deputies, high-ranking officials in city and regional councils). The size of the allocated housing largely depended on the recipient's social status (e.g., Hero of the Soviet Union, Honoured Bolshevik) or military rank (including post-demobilisation). Thus, a profound social inequality in access to housing existed in post-war Dnipropetrovsk.

For instance, a "major general (according to the USSR Council of Ministers Resolution No. 3616-1508 cc of August 21, 1950, on the allocation of housing to generals, admirals, and officers of the Soviet Army, under the 10% departmental housing fund)" (State Archive of Dnipropetrovsk Region: collection 416, inventory 2, file 346, folio 276) received a four-room apartment with a total area of 88 m², while a "family of a soldier killed during the Great Patriotic War" was granted just 10 m² (State Archive of Dnipropetrovsk Region: collection 416, inventory 2, file 357, folio 262). In 59 of 185 recorded housing allocations in 1950, the housing area was not indicated, likely reflecting concealed nepotism or possible corruption in the housing allocation bodies. These findings, along with others, support the existence of systemic rights violations in access to housing in Dnipropetrovsk and throughout the Ukrainian SSR at the time (Iankovska, 2008).

This pattern of housing inequality also existed in other high-priority Soviet cities and was not confined to the post-war Stalinist period but extended to the other years of Stalin's rule as well. In his work *Moscow: Governing the Socialist Metropolis*, Colton (1995), notes that under Stalin, apartments built by ministries and enterprises using their own resources differed sharply

in size and quality. A train operator at an aviation plant might receive a flat with one or two more rooms and better amenities than a worker at a textile factory or bakery, while an NKVD captain would live better than a school principal. Over time, Soviet housing policy increasingly favoured Soviet bureaucrats and the professional intelligentsia, placing them in far superior housing conditions compared to workers or junior clerks. According to the Law, “*Senior officials in government agencies and enterprises, professional, party, military, cooperative, and public organisations*” as well as Heroes of the Soviet Union, labour heroes, decorated veterans, and pensioners were entitled to additional housing space – ranging from 10.9 to 21.8 square yards (approximately 9.1–18.2 m²) per person without increased rent (Sosnovy, 1952). The Soviet bureaucracy was not a single group, but quite a heterogeneous entity. Its upper stratum, the ‘Soviet aristocracy’, could live in exceptionally favourable conditions while ordinary workers might be relegated to barracks with poor sanitary conditions (Sosnovy, 1952).

Housing allocation in Dnipropetrovsk during de-Stalinisation (1953-1964)

By the 1950s, Soviet authorities finally began to acknowledge the housing crisis plaguing Soviet society. Rapid urbanisation, coupled with a housing deficit in cities across the USSR, necessitated a qualitatively new approach to housing policy. In the early 1950s, a state housing construction program was launched, providing people with the hope of acquiring their own homes (Iankovska & Bachynskyj, 2013). Decisive measures included decrees by the Central Committee and the USSR Council of Ministers, such as *On Measures for Further Industrialization, Improving Quality and Reducing the Cost of Construction* (Central Committee, 1955), *On the Development of Housing Construction in the USSR* (Central Committee, 1957), and *On Individual and Cooperative Housing Construction* (Central Committee, 1962), the latter of which stimulated the development of housing cooperatives throughout the Soviet Union.

The housing reforms introduced under Khrushchev can be described as an ‘ideological revolution’ in the development of the Soviet housing sector. In particular, between 1957 and 1963, a fundamental shift in housing construction technology began in the USSR, following the proclamation by the Central Committee that every family should live in a separate apartment. The first new types of economy-class apartments were constructed in 1958 (Durmanov, 2010). In contemporary terms, Khrushchev’s housing campaign entailed a qualitative transition from communal to ‘single-family’ living (Varga-Harris, 2008). Soviet citizens who, in the 1940s, lived in makeshift houses or partially destroyed buildings without electricity or running water, were moved in the 1950s into apartments where they shared bathrooms and kitchens with other

families, and then, in the 1960s, into their own private apartments (Wright, 1970). Here, 'private apartments' refers to having personal space, rather than personal ownership.

Between 1956 and 1965, over 100 million Soviet citizens were relocated from overcrowded slums to new or renovated housing (Reid, 2011). While people were now afforded the possibility of obtaining their own living space, the process unfolded slowly. Individuals progressed slowly, though steadily, through the housing waiting lists for state, departmental, or cooperative apartments, often waiting for many years. A position on the housing list became one of the most valued forms of capital for the Soviet citizen. Advancement depended on one's productivity, participation in collective life, and relationship with supervisors – factors which allowed for considerable leverage and pressure on workers. Additionally, large industrial enterprises were granted the right to allocate a portion of their funds toward employee housing construction, while employees of smaller factories or the public sector had to wait for state-constructed housing allocated by local authorities, or for a share in housing built by enterprises (Iankovska & Bachynskyj, 2013).

The process of housing allocation was accelerated by the mass housing campaign launched in 1957, which adopted modern industrial methods such as standardisation and prefabrication to rehouse as many people as possible in the shortest possible time. The new apartments, nicknamed *khrushchyovki*, were standardised, simple, and bore little resemblance to the apartments of the Stalinist era. *Khrushchyovki* were designed for individual nuclear families, as opposed to communal apartments or barracks that had previously been the norm. By providing 'private' (i.e., separate) spaces for families, these buildings, like many twentieth-century housing projects, were also intended as instruments of social engineering and homogenisation (Reid, 2011).

Typically, five stories tall and of low construction quality, *khrushchyovki*, were colloquially referred to as *khrushchoby* (a portmanteau of *Khrushchev* and *thrushchoby*, i.e. slums). One possible explanation for their poor quality – apart from the economical use of state resources – was the assumption among specialists that the deliberate reduction in quality served to diminish envy toward the lucky few who received such mass-produced housing (Colton, 1995).

As revealed by archival materials for the studied period of 1960, the following set of procedures for the allocation of residential space existed in the city of Dnipropetrovsk (State Archive of Dnipropetrovsk Region, collection 416, inventory 2, file 930, folio 560-563)

- 1) Housing was allocated strictly in accordance with the waiting list, except in cases of relocation from emergency housing stock.
- 2) The allocation of residential space from the housing stock of local Council of Workers' Deputies, including the 10% share allocated to enterprises and organisations, was

carried out by the executive committees of district Soviets of Workers' Deputies, based on the waiting list, with the participation of the permanent housing commission, representatives of the district Council of Workers' Deputies, and the Regional Trade Union Council (or *Oblprofrada*).

- 3) The executive committees of district Councils of Workers' Deputies registered for housing assistance the following categories of individuals: war and labour invalids, families of deceased soldiers, reserve officers of the Soviet Army, veteran members of the Communist Party, personal pensioners, and other non-working citizens eligible under special government decrees. Citizens were accepted into the waiting list for housing if they: (a) had no living space at all; (b) were residing in substandard or hazardous housing, including basements; or (c) were in urgent need of alternative accommodation. Citizens were entered into the official housing waiting list on the basis of decisions made by the district executive committees.
- 4) The following categories of citizens were not eligible to be registered for municipal housing assistance by the executive committees of district councils: (a) citizens employed at enterprises, organisations, or institutions that possessed departmental housing stock, received housing from the city executive committee of the Councils of Workers' Deputies, or were undertaking individual housing construction; (b) citizens who owned residential properties as private (personal) property; (c) citizens who had been allocated land plots for individual housing development.
- 5) At industrial enterprises, organisations, and institutions, registration for housing allocation included the opening of a housing file and entry into the housing queue ledger. This applied to citizens employed at or connected through labour relations to these enterprises, organisations, and institutions, including those until their retirement.

The analysis also revealed the existence of certain 'soft' factors influencing the distribution of housing in Dnipropetrovsk during the de-Stalinisation era. In particular, the size of allocated living space depended on: (1) the employee's length of service and the number of family members working at a particular enterprise, organisation, or institution; (2) the number of household members and the presence of young children; (3) the military rank of servicemen (including demobilised soldiers); (4) the social status of the recipient. Additionally, the archival records from the de-Stalinisation period reveal hidden social inequalities in the housing allocation process. For instance, one unidentified recipient, whose household consisted of three persons, received a three-room apartment with a living area of 52.5 m², whereas another recipient, with a family of five, was allocated an apartment of the same size in the same

building. This is illustrated by the decision of the Dnipropetrovsk City Executive Committee No. 392 of April 30, 1960, as shown at figure 2.

Compared to the previous period, there was an increase in the diversity of social groups receiving apartments. Besides military personnel, veterans and disabled persons of the Great Patriotic War, and nomenklatura, there were also representatives of the intelligentsia (scientists, leading athletes, actors, among others) and a broader segment of the working class. Thus, although de-Stalinisation led to a relative decrease in social inequality in housing distribution compared to the Stalinist period, it remained notably high. The analysis also revealed gender inequality in housing allocation, favouring men, since, according to archival data, the majority of housing recipients were men. This was linked to the gender imbalance in the Dnipropetrovsk labour market, largely due to the city's heavy industrial economy (e.g., ferrous metallurgy, mechanical engineering). Another feature of housing distribution during de-Stalinisation, similar to the Stalinist period, was the concealment of social inequalities: the living area allocated to representatives of the intelligentsia and individuals with honorary titles was often not specified in official documents.

Figure 2: Example of hidden social inequality in the housing allocation during de-Stalinisation (authors' own photography State Archive of Dnipropetrovsk Region, collection 416, inventory 2, file 913, folio 357-35)

Thus, the consequences of Khrushchev's housing reforms included: (1) a sharp quantitative increase in the volume of housing construction (at times exceeding the rate of urban population growth); and (2) a qualitative shift toward mass construction of individual apartments, replacing the practice of room-by-room settlement with family-based occupation of new housing (Iankovska & Bachynskij, 2013). Moreover, the de-Stalinisation period marked a

transition from elitism or favouritism to relative egalitarianism within the Soviet system of housing distribution and access to better living conditions. During Khrushchev's era, the private apartment became "housing for the people" rather than a privilege limited to the "middle class" or elite segments of the state and the Communist Party (Varga-Harris, 2008).

Housing allocation in Dnipropetrovsk in late socialism (1964–1985)

The era of late socialism in the Soviet Union and other communist countries of Europe is associated with the mass construction of standardised large-scale housing estates (microrayons). From the 1960s onwards, a new factor of intra-urban structural transformation emerged in most socialist Central European countries: the construction of extensive residential estates. These developments were predominantly located in the peripheral zones of cities and significantly altered their urban structure (Musil, 1993). Under late socialism, family status became the main condition for obtaining an apartment, as apartments in panel-built residential estates during the 1970s and 1980s were primarily allocated to young married couples with children (Kubeš, 2013).

The period of developed socialism was characterised by the rapid spatial expansion of Dnipropetrovsk. On one hand, this territorial expansion was driven by a new wave of residential construction (the development of new housing estates, residential microrayons, etc.), and on the other hand, by the vigorous economic growth of the city.

By examining archival materials on housing allocation among Dnipropetrovsk residents during the surveyed periods of 1970 and 1979, and based on fieldwork experience, the following features were identified:

- The city's economic development stimulated an influx of new specialists who were promised housing as an incentive for relocating and employment at specific enterprises, organisations, or institutions.
- Housing was sometimes allocated to individuals living in the suburban areas whose places of employment were located within Dnipropetrovsk.
- Participation in the construction of a residential neighbourhood or building also provided additional privileges for faster access to housing.
- Compared to the Stalinist and de-Stalinisation periods, a shift from communal housing to family housing was evident during late socialism. Furthermore, unlike in the de-Stalinisation period, the needs of different generations were taken into account. For instance, adult children were expected to live separately from their parents, and a young family expecting a child could qualify for a larger apartment.

- Other mechanisms, such as the hazardous condition of a building or its location within a future construction site, also allowed residents to obtain housing more quickly. Additionally, apartment exchanges were used to improve housing conditions.
- A new phenomenon of social inequality emerged – vertical residential segregation: citizens of higher social status or those with strong connections to the nomenklatura received apartments on the 2nd (3rd) to 5th (6th) floors of multi-storey buildings, which were considered more desirable due to better living conditions and compliance with medical standards regarding optimal living height.
- Under late socialism, the level of social inequality in housing distribution declined significantly compared to the two earlier periods under study. However, a certain degree of gender inequality (in favour of men) in access to faster housing acquisition opportunities still persisted.

Archival materials also indicate that nepotism, as a shadow side of the centralised housing allocation system, did not disappear during the period of late socialism. A possible example of this is found in one of the numerous executive committee decisions from 1970 (State Archive of Dnipropetrovsk Region, collection 416, inventory 2, file 1578, folios 169, 187), where a male correspondent for the newspaper *Socialist Industry* was granted a four-room apartment on the third floor of a building (without specification of household size) with an area of 85.26 m² (with the note: “*taking into account the organisation of a correspondence office at home*”). By contrast, in the same year, the city executive committee decided to allocate a three-room apartment on the fifth floor, with an area of 57.72 m², to a male skilled worker from the combine plant whose household consisted of six persons (State Archive of Dnipropetrovsk Region, collection 416, inventory 2, file 1578, folios 169, 169, 177). Moreover, the archival materials show that the allocation of housing in Soviet Dnipro was heavily influenced by the city’s economic structure. Enterprises possessed a certain portion of the urban housing stock, both actual and planned, which simultaneously impacted the housing allocation system and the patterns of urban settlement. With a high degree of certainty, it can be stated that most enterprises, wherever possible, sought to ensure that their workers lived close to their places of employment, often attempting to settle employees within the same building, neighbourhood, microrayon, or part of the city.

Housing allocation in Dnipropetrovsk in late socialism (1964–1985) in view of in-depth interviews

As noted above, the in-depth interview materials concern the late socialism period. The logic of presentation here is as follows. First, we provide participants' testimonies about the influence of their social, property, professional status, and other factors on both the speed of obtaining housing and its quality. Next, particular attention is paid to such factors of housing inequality as residence in a 'closed' city and employment at a strategically important or influential enterprise. The following part of the testimonies relates to informal, shadow practices that affected housing allocation outcomes and flourished under late socialism. Finally, the issue of 'vertical' inequality is considered, namely the dependence of housing quality on the floor level within the same building, as well as related aspects of housing quality (such as wall material, corner vs. non-corner apartments).

An important aspect for understanding the social composition of housing recipients during the late socialist period is the observation of a relative egalitarianism in the distribution of housing. The residents of her brezhnevka-type apartment block were *"Completely diverse. Engineers, office workers, teachers, kindergarten educators. A mixed group. [...] One cannot say there was selective allocation. If your turn comes, you receive the apartment"* (HD1). Thus, a social mix was present in large Soviet housing estates, reflecting the relative egalitarianism embedded in the housing allocation system of that period.

The experiences of participants or their families in obtaining housing were highly diverse. On one hand, there were positive experiences related to being placed on a waiting list for the improvement of housing conditions. For instance, the parents of HD1 received an apartment in the newly built state-funded residential district. As a result, they moved from a one-room apartment located on the first floor of a Khrushchev-era building to a better apartment situated on the third floor of a nine-story Brezhnev-era apartment block: *"I don't remember exactly how long we waited in line – not very long. Maybe two or three years. This was largely due to the fact that my father was a school principal"* (HD1). On the other hand, not everyone managed to obtain an apartment quickly. For instance, other participant reports that he was placed on a waiting list for housing in the 1970s, but received an apartment only at the transition between the late socialist period and the perestroika era: *"The Ministry issued an order to provide me with housing – either granting an apartment or placing me on a preferential waiting list. A young specialist was supposed to receive housing within three years. But that was unrealistic. I waited 13 years"* (HD2).

These two contrasting experiences of obtaining an apartment in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk indicate that social, professional, and family status significantly influenced the speed of

obtaining housing. Another important factor affecting the (un)successfulness of acquiring housing in the ‘closed’ Soviet city was the migrant or local resident status. One participant emphasised that, during the administrative allocation of housing, preference was often given to local residents: *“Most often [apartments were given to] locals. There were certain traditions. There was a strong sense of patriotism at the city level”* (HD2). At the same time, another participant (HD5) believes that being a local resident or a newcomer had little influence on the allocation of housing in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk. However, HD5 had lived in Dnipropetrovsk since childhood, whereas HD2 arrived in the city as a young specialist and encountered the Soviet bureaucratic system. Another resident of Soviet Dnipropetrovsk noted that newcomers *“were given housing more quickly [...]. They were immediately provided with a place in a dormitory or a small family apartment”* (HD6). It is important to stress that, according to HD6, newcomers were not given fully-fledged apartments, but merely minimal housing provisions, such as rooms in dormitories or small family units.

Participant HD3 also emphasises that in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, at the turn between the de-Stalinisation era and late socialism, apartments were allocated slowly, that is, people had to wait in line for a long time, but over time, the process began to accelerate. Another participant reports that the process of centralised housing distribution in the city was *“very difficult, tricky. There were different queues. The general queue moved slowly. The second one was preferential. That included people with disabilities, meritorious [citizens], perhaps large families. It moved faster – three to four years. But for those in the regular queue, it was 15–20 years. It couldn’t go faster. It was very complicated.”* (HD4)

As noted above, archival materials indicated the presence of some gender inequality in the allocation of housing. However, the results of in-depth interviews suggest the opposite: *“[Housing was allocated] equally. There was no [discrimination]. [...] If a woman was more professional, she received [an apartment]”* (HD1); *“I worked in an organisation affiliated with the automobile plant. Two young women worked there. Both received apartments. [...] I cannot say that women faced discrimination. A single person could receive one, if lucky enough”* (HD4); *“Women probably applied for housing less often, but if a woman had the opportunity to get an apartment, the wife would submit the application”* (HD5). This indicates that the process of administrative housing allocation was characterised not so much by gender discrimination, but rather by discrimination based on marital status (i.e., singles versus families).

Evidence of social inequality in the housing allocation process can be found in the responses of other participants as well. Overall, one of the most discriminated social groups in the housing distribution system was young specialists. Although they were a privileged category under Soviet law, their legal entitlement to expedited housing was often ignored amid the

overall housing shortage: *“Although enterprises were supposed to provide housing to young specialists, I don’t know of any cases where they did, even though [they] were obligated to.”* (HD5).

Membership in the Communist Party influenced the speed of receiving housing and access to better living conditions, although this primarily applied to the middle and upper tiers of the “servants” of communism: *“Those who were in the Party had all the advantages. [...] Party members got the housing. [...] Did people receive housing through the Party? All Party members lived in the city centre, in good apartments. None of them went to the outskirts. [...] All the high-ranking Party members did. The lower-level ones weren’t given apartments. But the bosses – they lived in another dimension”* (HD4); *“Party members were the first to be allocated housing”* (HD5); *“People who held high-ranking Party positions received decent apartments and land plots, unlike ordinary Party members”* (HD7). Nevertheless, some participants asserted the contrary: *“Party membership did not influence access to apartments”* (HD6).

A noticeable difference was also observed in the timing of apartment allocation between industrial workers and employees in the social sector. As one participant noted, white-collar workers received apartments *“somewhat more slowly”* (HD2) than blue-collar workers employed at industrial enterprises. Others emphasised that *“managers were given the best places [apartments]”* (HD3); *“The elite could get better apartments”* (HD6). Another participant explained that social-sector workers were included *“in the general waiting list of the city executive committee. Whatever number of apartments the city allocated – some would go to teachers, doctors, some to smaller factories”* (HD4). Military personnel were treated as a special category: *“There were even separate queues among the military. There was a military quota. A waiting list at the military commissariat. After leaving service, they would receive housing”* (HD4). Also, participant HD4 shared a revealing example of how his father-in-law, a military officer, received housing more quickly than social-sector workers: *“My wife’s father completed his military service in Azerbaijan and moved here to Dnipropetrovsk. [...] They received an apartment [...] thanks to a preferential military housing quota. Meanwhile, others stood in line for 15 years with children. [...] The military were slightly better supported. They were prioritised. [...] Social-sector workers had to wait much longer, on average, in line with the rest of the city. They could be lucky in 10 years”*.

Additionally, some workers at strategic enterprises enjoyed certain advantages in the housing allocation process. As several participants recalled: *“There were some benefits at that plant. It wasn’t just the city that was closed; the factory itself was even more so. [...] Not everyone received housing through the factory’s own housing stock – only management and distinguished workers did. [...] Other workers received housing on general grounds. [...] They*

waited 15 to 16 years or more” (HD2); “Some of my acquaintances at Pivdenmash received housing faster. One family first got a small apartment, then had another child, and received a larger one. The quality wasn’t great, but it was faster. My friend’s husband worked as an engineer at the Pivdenmash tractor division. Those in the space division received the same apartments as everyone else, but faster. They also didn’t have to work on the construction site. [...] There were no special privileges for ordinary workers and engineers” (HD6). Pivdenmash and specific supervisors at the plant played a decisive role for one of the participants receiving an apartment: “I was on the waiting list, but they removed me [because I didn’t have a family]. [...] I had a good supervisor who intervened in my life [...] she told them put me back” (HD3).

Other participants emphasise the extent to which the housing allocation process depended on the status of the enterprise: *“Many enterprises carried out their own construction. Smaller ones could not afford it. [...] At the Metalist Plant many people received housing. Large factories could allow that. [...] Some factories also built housing cooperatives. [...] Our Pivdennyi Machine-Building Plant constructed a lot of housing. It was a city within a city. Even in our residential area, there were several 16-story buildings” (HD4); “The wealthier and larger the enterprise was, the faster one could receive an apartment” (HD6).*

Another factor that accelerated the process of obtaining an apartment in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk was direct participation in the construction of the building. For example, participant HD6 notes that when she was two years old, her parents received a corner apartment on the fourth floor of a panel building (constructed in 1970), and for this, her father *“worked on the construction of this building for half a year on weekends as a general labourer” (HD6).*

As the participants note while describing and comparing Soviet Dnipropetrovsk with other cities of the former USSR at the time, *“The closed city had its own autonomous standards of life. We were independent – more independent from Kyiv, from Ukrainian bureaucratic structures. And we were distant from Moscow. Dnipropetrovsk could dictate its own terms. The key industries – Pivdenmash and the major metallurgical giants like the Petrovskiy, Lenin, and Babushkin plants – ensured more order. And apartments were received more quickly here.” (HD2).* However, participant HD5 emphasises that the status of a ‘closed’ city did not affect the quality of the housing stock or the speed of receiving an apartment: *“Standardised designs, building codes, state standards – everything was constructed the same way. The same enterprises built the houses. So, I don’t think this [the ‘closed’ city status] influenced [housing quality or allocation speed]”. Similarly, HD7 adds that the ‘closed’ city status did not translate into a significantly better housing stock: “To say there was something exceptional – no.*

Everything was standard. A khrushchyovka was still a khrushchyovka, and a panel building was just a panel building”.

The shadow side of administrative housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk included shadow realty market, informal patronage networks, bribery, and squatting: *“People pushed their way in. Sometimes people moved out, exchanged apartments, or had their unit transferred to the city executive committee’s stock. That unit could then be quickly reallocated. Phone calls were made, and it was given away. These things were often resolved interpersonally. But speculation occurred. It was easy to conceal irregularities in the housing stock. So apartments were speculated upon. Sometimes even criminals obtained housing. One person, living alone, might get a three-room apartment. Not often. But it caused outrage. Still, people tolerated it. That was ‘positional privilege.’ [...] A secretary of the city executive committee could remove some apartments from the queue. One, two, three, even ten. He could give them to his godfather, friends, acquaintances, in-laws. There were shadow schemes. The shadow economy emerged during perestroika”* (HD2); *“There were shady dealings in the queue. People were assigned numbers. But later that number could increase. It was impossible to find out who had been pushed ahead. You were number 120. [...] You came back and suddenly you were number 136”* (HD4); *“You could bribe someone and get an apartment. [...] At my workplace, there was a case during the dissolution of a communal apartment. One man with a family just stayed put until everyone else was relocated. He was the only one left in the communal unit. He ended up with a luxurious apartment in a five-story Stalin-era building in the city centre. People would bribe the trade union committee to move up the queue. Or have more children”* (HD6); *“When a building is demolished, each family receives a separate apartment. [...] Once it became known that resettlement would take place, people started registering their residency there. It was not so much about bribes as about connections: a favour for a favour [...] People registered relatives or acquaintances retroactively”* (HD4); *“They gave me the 5th floor. I was very happy. I was afraid someone might occupy it. Once, my father was assigned an apartment on the 2nd floor, but a woman had already moved in. [She said:] ‘Over my dead body’ [you will evict me]”* (HD3).

There were also cases where people received better living conditions independent of administrative favouritism, though such favouritism may have influenced earlier stages of the housing allocation process: (1) being added to the waiting list and (2) advancing within the queue. Participant (HD4) described an exceptional case when he received a “prestigious” fourth-floor apartment: *“I got the fourth floor by chance, via a lottery. Not always were apartments assigned directly through organisations. There was a lottery for three-room and*

two-room units”. However, personal connections still played a role: *“Despite the lottery, the best apartments stayed within the families [of those in charge of the allocation process]”* (HD4).

The most desirable floors (in Soviet tradition, floors are numerated starting from the ground floor, which is considered as the 1st floor) in the process of housing allocation were *“from the 2nd to the 4th. Many people made decisions based on the elevator availability, so they wouldn’t have to climb too high with heavy bags”* (HD7); *“The ground [floor] was the worst, while the third and fourth, reachable by foot, were the most comfortable”* (HD5); *“Better to be on the second floor, but not on the top. Not the ground, not the top floor”* (HD2); *“When apartments were being allocated, no one wanted the ground or top floor. Noise, dirt. Trash chutes were close to the entrances on the ground floors. It was a nightmare – rats and cockroaches [...] People didn’t want the 8th or 9th floors in nine-story buildings either. Quality wasn’t great. The elevators often broke down. [...] The 4th and 5th floors were [the best] in nine-story buildings. You could walk up without the elevator”* (HD4); *“If there was a choice, people picked the south side. They’d ask: ‘Is it north-facing?’ If there was [another] building nearby or a low floor – it was always bad, always dark”* (HD4); *“The most popular were floors 3rd to 5th. No one cared much about which side of the building. Corner apartments were taken last. The ground floor was considered undesirable. Even the 9th was better”* (HD6).

Different architectural designs of housing were used in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk. *“The Czech project [the buildings] were warmer, brick-built. The panel [buildings] were cold. But even the Czech buildings had problems: corners were built in such a way that they were also cold and damp. Maybe they used thinner walls or did something wrong. Corner apartments were later hard to sell”*. Corner units were *“cold and damp. Even today they’re being insulated. Construction companies and the housing maintenance office used to seal the joints. In winter, there were drafts”* (HD4). Another participant summarised the situation clearly: *“Just like today, [corner apartments] weren’t highly regarded. Being in the middle [of the building] was better”* (HD5). Even in relatively better buildings, the last floor suffered from the usual issues: *“The building was very well designed [departmental housing], in a central elite neighbourhood. [...] The only issue was the roof leaked. I had to become a roofer myself and tarred the eaves”* (HD2).

Conclusions

This section synthesises the main findings of the study in relation to the research questions outlined at the outset, situates them within the broader scholarly debate on socio-spatial inequality in socialist and post-socialist cities, and reflects on their implications for contemporary housing policy and urban development.

Returning to the three research questions defined at the beginning of this article, we can state the following. Answering the first question, we found that social inequality in the process of administrative housing allocation and access to better housing conditions in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk did exist, although it softened over time from the 1950s to the 1980s, while acquiring new forms. At the beginning of the studied period the issue was access to housing as such, while at the end it was about housing in a better area, a better house, a better floor or side of the house, or other improvement.

Answering the second question, it was found that social inequality in access to rapid housing acquisition and improved living conditions in the Soviet 'closed' city can be described using the following triad. At the top were the nomenklatura (the 'ruling class'), the intelligentsia, and white-collar workers, who either possessed privileges or had connections with those who could facilitate access to better housing. At the bottom were the grey-collar workers (i.e., employees in the social services sector), who were less favoured in terms of quick housing acquisition and thus had to wait much longer in the queue. Positioned between the base and the apex of the social stratification were the blue-collar workers, who could obtain housing more quickly than the grey-collar workers. However, within this social stratum, further differentiation existed depending on the worker's professional skills, loyalty to the enterprise, and the priority and strategic importance of the enterprise. Exceptions within this triad occurred due to the existence of nepotism, a parallel 'housing market' (where apartment exchanges were possible), or unlawful practices such as the forced resettlement of individuals into dilapidated buildings requiring urgent relocation into new apartments.

Summarising the results of the study across three historical periods of housing sector development in the Soviet high-priority metropolis, it can be concluded that in Dnipropetrovsk there was a clear 'class-based' social inequality in housing distribution and access to better living conditions. The nomenklatura and other elite groups received larger apartments constructed with better-quality materials, whereas ordinary urban proletarians were housed first in communal apartments, later in *khrushchyovka* flats, and subsequently in standardised panel-built high-rise blocks (figure 3). 'Proletarian' buildings were often constructed with low-quality materials, and the apartments within them were sometimes in poor condition at the time of commissioning. These findings confirm the existence of significant social inequality in the process of command-administrative housing distribution in the case study city.

As shown in figure 4, there was a vertical (i.e. floor-dependent) housing inequality in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk in terms of housing quality, which directly depended on the social status of the housing recipient. During the periods of post-war Stalinism and de-Stalinisation, vertical housing inequality was at a nascent stage, while during late socialism it became more

pronounced. In addition to vertical housing inequality, disparities existed in relation to (non-)corner and (non-)end apartments, as well as apartments located on the (non-)sunny sides of buildings.

Based on the findings described above and the empirical experience of studying Soviet Dnipropetrovsk, it can be asserted with regard to the third research question that the city's high-priority status contributed to a larger share of privileged residents compared to ordinary open cities. As a result, in the 'closed' city of Dnipropetrovsk, there was a more widespread and pronounced social divide in the process of housing allocation and access, as well as in the quality of living conditions. This included not only fragmented horizontal housing inequality (such as designated housing or hotels for the nomenklatura, closed residential complexes for employees of special enterprises), but also vertical housing inequality in terms of the quality of living conditions within urban neighbourhoods of Khrushchev-era and Brezhnev-era housing blocks. In particular, the post-war elitist policy of housing allocation laid the foundation for striking social inequalities, which were gradually softened during the periods of de-Stalinisation and late socialism. Thus, it is possible to partially confirm the hypothesis regarding the 'closed city' effect on the intensification and complication of social inequality in the area of housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk.

In this way, this article at least partially addresses the identified research gap and complements existing understandings of socio-spatial stratification in socialist cities by demonstrating that the status of a 'closed' Soviet city was an additional factor that intensified social disparities in access to housing – both within such cities themselves and in comparison with ordinary cities. It is also shown that the forms of housing inequality evolved from strict and explicit ones (the very possibility of obtaining housing) to softer and more hidden ones (the possibility of obtaining better housing or obtaining it more quickly), in line with the evolution of Soviet housing policy and the situation regarding the quantity and quality of newly constructed housing.

Figure 3: Patterns of housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk during the post-war Stalinism, de-Stalinisation, and late socialism. Elaborated by the authors

Figure 4: Patterns of vertical inequalities in housing conditions under housing allocation in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk (from left to right, schematically depicted: stalinka, a 5-story khrushchyovka, and a 9-story brezhnevka). The vertical axis represents the number of building floors. Elaborated by the authors

The findings of this paper are significant for several reasons. First, they contribute to the discussion about the nature and fairness of the administrative-command housing allocation system that existed under socialism, highlighting an additional dimension of socio-spatial effects related to high-priority 'closed' cities and enriching in this way the discussion related to the forms, drivers, manifestations and consequences of the spatial (un)justice in different

socio-cultural and socio-political contexts (Soja, 2010; Moroni & De Franco, 2024; Dadashpoor & Dehghan, 2025).

Second, the socialist experience of housing allocation may be of interest even in modern market economies where state participates in the housing allocation in some form. For instance, contemporary Ukraine faces the urgent challenge of solving a housing crisis caused by the Russo-Ukrainian war, similar in many respects to the situation the Soviet Union faced after the Second World War. There may be a temptation to adopt certain elements of the Soviet model, particularly those related to the distribution of social housing to the most vulnerable or 'deserving' segments of the population. Under socialism, at least at the level of declared principles, the principle of need-based fairness was upheld. In market conditions, this approach may be useful for social and municipal housing programs to avoid the marginalisation of the most vulnerable groups. For housing distribution to be perceived by society as fair, it must take place according to transparent and clearly defined rules and criteria. Under socialism, such criteria formally existed. Balancing these criteria with market mechanisms can enhance public trust in social housing programs, as it integrates normative principles of allocation with economic incentives, thereby reducing perceptions of arbitrariness and increasing transparency and legitimacy. Another positive aspect of socialist housing policy was the integration of housing with infrastructure: the microrayon concept envisaged the simultaneous construction of housing, social infrastructure, and the creation of green public spaces. Under the neoliberal approach to urban planning, particularly in contemporary Ukraine, these requirements are largely ignored by developers (Dronova et al., 2021). The Soviet practice of housing cooperatives is also worth reconsidering, provided it is adapted to contemporary market-based conditions, including the establishment of transparent financing schemes, clearly defined property rights, mechanisms for private-public collaboration, and planning regulations that ensure accountability, affordability, and the provision of social and green infrastructure. What should be avoided are non-participatory decisions regarding housing policies (in a democratic society, the approval of housing distribution rules should be preceded by broad public discussion involving diverse stakeholders, including minority and vulnerable groups), monopolisation of housing allocation, preferences for certain categories of cities, and ignoring housing quality in favour of quantity (low-quality mass housing for ordinary consumers, monotonous urban landscapes; notably, in post-Soviet Ukraine, social housing is usually of significantly lower quality and is located in remote, non-prestigious urban areas unattractive to commercial developers). Yet, many of the deficiencies of housing allocation under socialism are being replicated in independent Ukraine in the field of social housing distribution (Zapotoskyi et al., 2021; Zapototska et al., 2025).

Third, the spatial patterns of housing inequality originating in the socialist era, including their horizontal and vertical dimensions, appear to be remarkably persistent and remain visible even decades after the collapse of socialism in various parts of Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern Europe, where the socialist system left a strong imprint on urban landscapes (Gentile, 2015; Gentile & Marcińczak, 2014). Thus, to understand the socio-spatial patterns of a post-socialist city, it is often still necessary to consider the foundational factors and structures established during the socialist era (Kalyukin & Kohl, 2020).

Overall, the findings of this study demonstrate that the ‘closed’ city status constituted a distinct and previously underexplored driver of socio-spatial housing inequality, shaping both its intensity and its specific manifestations in Soviet Dnipropetrovsk.

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Conflict of interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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